

ITC Digital Transformation of the Working World

Working Paper Series, Nr. 001/2020

ISSN: xxxx

25 July 2020

Early Identification of Convergence as an Opportunity for Competence Development

Authors*

Simon Zemp*, Ute Klotz*

*Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts – Information Technology, Campus Zug-Rotkreuz, and Interdisciplinary Theme Cluster (ITC) «Digital Transformation of the Working World», Suurstoffli 1a, Rotkreuz, Switzerland, simon.zemp@hslu.ch

Cite this paper as:

Zemp, S. & Klotz, U. (2020). Early identification of convergence as an opportunity for competence development. ITC Digital Transformation of the Working World Working Paper 001/2020, Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts.

Abstract

Innovation is crucial for many organizations and industries aiming to maintain a competitive edge in national and international markets. That innovations can be created in a multitude of ways is a well-known fact. One possibility considered here are cross-industry innovations, as in those innovations that seek to transfer existing processes and technologies from other industries into their own sector, and then use them to generate more innovations. The main difficulties facing such an endeavor is, amongst others, the ability to identify the relevant extra-industry processes and technologies, successfully integrating them into one's own knowledge structure, and implementing them in a company-specific application.

Keywords: innovation, cross-industry knowledge, organizational learning, industry convergence, absorptive capacity, knowledge theory, mental models

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	4
2. Convergence – Definition and Differentiation	4
3. Theoretical Foundations of Convergence	7
4. Promoting Absorptive Capacity	9
5. Next Steps / Further Action	11
References	12

1. Introduction

Many businesses find it difficult to further develop their competences in the context of digitalization, innovation management, and industry convergence. There are numerous reasons for this. In terms of industry convergence, the challenge for companies lies not only in identifying and determining the relevant extra-industry knowledge, but also in successfully integrating and further developing it in their business on both the individual and organizational levels. Early identification of convergence knowledge can be based on, among other things, a patent analysis of the technology classes (Song, 2016, p. 251; Lee, 2105, p. 63, Curran, Bröring & Leker, 2010, p. 388), a monitoring of technology trends (p. 237), an industry structure analysis (p. 221) and a search for analogies (Kerl, 2018, p. 27, cited in Dürrmüller & Enkel, 2011). But an early identification of new intra-industry and extra-industry technologies is not sufficient to be innovative. What is crucial is integrating this knowledge into the company's existing knowledge base. And thus, the central question here: To what extent can identified extra-industry knowledge be successfully appropriated on an individual or organizational basis?

2. Convergence – Definition and Differentiation

Convergence is interdisciplinary (Song, 2016, p. 3). It can connect and combine knowledge, technology, and applications of otherwise separate and distinct disciplines and across different levels of an organization (Roco & Bainbridge, 2013, p. 7) in an «evolutionary development and change process» (Song, 2016, p. 94). According to Song (2016, p. 3), convergence is a popular term in the business world and serves as a motivation to research and engage with other industry sectors.

A convergence process is ideally carried out in four steps:

- It all starts with *knowledge convergence* (Song, 2016, p. 100) or *scientific convergence* (Curran, Bröring & Leker, 2010, p. 386). According to Bainbridge (2006, p. 24), researchers often tend to explore related subjects from other fields when progress in their own subject area becomes more difficult. This is typically expressed in co-citation between distinct scientific disciplines and this cross-referencing can lead to a collaboration (cooperation) (Curran, Bröring & Leker, 2010, p. 386). Ideally, once the gap between the different disciplines narrows, applied science and technical development should follow, which then should lead to technology convergence (Curran, Bröring & Leker, 2010, p. 386; Song, 2016, p. 101).
- *Technology convergence* is then the integration of different technologies, in particular, with information and communication technologies, which then leads to a new product or function (Lee, 2015, p. 3). This may not be evident as such to the consumer (Song, 2016, p. 101). According to Wieland (2007), technology convergence is more important for the service provider because ultimately the customer only wants to use the product (p. 46).
- *Market convergence* changes the boundaries of at least two distinctly separate markets (Stieglitz, 2004, p. 25). Stieglitz distinguishes between two types of market convergence: (1) demand-side product convergence, when product characteristics change due to product innovation, and (2) supply-side technology convergence, when production technologies in both markets change. Furthermore, he makes a distinction between substitutive and complementary product convergence. In the former, two products are increasingly perceived as substitute products, i.e. the product characteristics have changed accordingly, and the two markets have converged. In the second case,

the products are used in a complementary way and are thus expected to generate greater benefits (p. 25).

- *Industrial convergence* occurs when previously separate industries and markets grow together. Convergence facilitates the merging of companies or areas of knowledge and blurs industrial boundaries (Song, 2016, p. 80).

The idealized convergence process can be summarized as follows:

Figure 1: Idealized Process of Convergence Processes (Curran, Bröring & Leker, 2010, p.387)

An *example* of industrial convergence is nutraceuticals, i.e. the merging of the food (nutra) and pharmaceutical industries. Here, we have convergence on both the input side (technology) and the output side (product/market), and each of the original industries is supplemented (complementary) (Bröring, 2007, p. 329). Drivers for this industry convergence are, on the technology side, the developments in biotechnology, which provide opportunities for new active substances and ingredients, and, on the product/market side, increased consumer interest in wellness and health. Nutraceuticals include foods with functional ingredients and products for individualized nutrition based on the genetic findings of each consumer (Bröring, 2007, pp. 329-331). Examples include calcium-fortified cereals to strengthen bones or eggs with omega-3 fatty acids that reduce the risk of heart attacks (Hinden, 2007).

Industry convergence can have several effects (Song (2016, p. 131):

One possible impact is *changes in the value chains*. This can lead to vertical integration (Lang, 2003, p. 3) or vertical disintegration (Brusoni & Pavitt, 2003, p. 4). Lang (2003) describes vertical integration as value creation convergence and believes that previously independent companies grow together at different stages of the value chain (p. 2). In addition to vertical disintegration or integration, these changes can also attract *new companies* into the convergence market due to its new business potential (Müller, 2008, p. 74).

For industrial convergence to take place, the new products or services must generate customer benefits that are *also economically worthwhile*. This involves primarily convenience products that are «consumer-centric» and offer new business opportunities, rather than technological development (BITKOM, 2005, p. 8).

Industrial convergence can also mean that earlier success factors may no longer be effective. This specifically includes *traditional management concepts*, for example, of how to implement industrial convergence on an organizational level (Bierly & Chakrabarti, 1999, p. 8). Hamel (1996, p.7) adds that *corporate strategy* is developed by the most experienced senior management. However, when industries change, this very experience no longer carries the same significance and becomes dangerous. According to Song (2016, p. 139), organizations must therefore be able to respond to changing customer demands without having to constantly change their corporate business strategy.

Bierly and Chakrabarti (1999, pp. 10-11) name *critical success factors* that they consider to be important for making an industrial convergence successful. First, it requires a clear vision of future products, customers, and competitors after the industrial convergence. Second (Bierly & Chakrabarti, 1996, p. 125), it necessitates the ability to integrate different critical knowledge areas into the company. This also means finding out how much of each field knowledge specialists and generalists actually need to successfully integrate it into the other field. And third, (Bierly & Chakrabarti, 1999, p. 11) it requires a good and effective working relationship with partners and representatives of different networks. This is to ensure that the company can continue to concentrate on its own core competencies.

As early as 1997—over 20 years ago—the European Commission (1997, p. iii) pointed out that industrial convergence between the telecommunications, media, and information technology sectors is more than just about technology. It is about services, new business models, and the interaction of

citizens in a society. In a broader sense, it is also about the future skills of individuals and their employability, as well as the values that should be lived in a society.

3. Theoretical Foundations of Convergence

Industrial convergence is forcing companies to expand their existing competencies with knowledge from other industries. Convergent innovations therefore often require companies to make an actual technological leap. However, given the dynamic nature of the business environment, developing in-house resources can be a protracted process. In the context of industrial convergence, it therefore makes sense to grow and fill the gaps in organizational capabilities by acquiring external knowledge through cooperation with research institutions or other companies (Kogut & Zander, 1992, p. 395).

However, the process of relevant knowledge acquisition is mired with cognitive obstacles. Quite often, the type of knowledge needed to direct complex innovation processes is unclear. This is particularly the case when transferring existing knowledge to a new application context or when integrating new types of knowledge into existing competencies, as is the case with industrial convergence. The lack of experience makes it difficult to assess new knowledge (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990, p. 132).

To process new knowledge, people fall back on mental models formed in the past. These interpretation patterns are based on individual experiences and form a kind of knowledge repository of assumptions, cause and effect relationships, and values (Bach, 2000, p. 3). The advantage of these cognitive structures is that they serve as orientation. Individuals with a limited information processing capacity can direct their perception to relevant areas ("selective perception", Neisser, 1996, p. 21), and thereby perceive and faster absorb new relevant knowledge. In so doing, they link the recorded data with cognitive processing patterns and form mental representations of reality (Neisser, 1996, p. 21).

Mental models therefore impact innovation processes by preserving decisionmakers' cognitive resources, thus enabling rapid solutions to complex challenges. However, the reliance on mental models makes both individual perception and information processing path dependent: New developments are perceived and interpreted against the background of existing experiential knowledge and integrated into existing knowledge structures. Learning thus takes place on the basis of what has already been learned and thus becomes path dependent (Obloy & Obloy & Pratt, 2010, p. 162).

The view taken here therefore contradicts the idea of objective information as concrete data that are available per se. Knowledge and information do not exist as such, but rather are bound by the specific mental structures of the respective observer. Therefore, the coherence of what is presumed to be relevant knowledge for innovation processes cannot achieve absolute validity, making an objective collection of information not possible. Rather, the members of an organization filter the data that appear to be useful and integrate them into the existing mental structures (Neisser, 1996, p. 21).

Information relevant for innovation processes, in particular, is characterized by unclear causal relationships and indistinct characteristics. In the presence of ambiguity, cognitive thought models play a special role, as they make it possible to assign meaning to vague information. And so, the process of constructing meaning occurs on the basis of decision bias: From the continuous flow of events, indicators ("cues") are constructed, which are extracted in the form of actions and their results. These indicators are interpreted with the help of mental models, which in turn are based on past experiences (see as a basis the process of "sensemaking" Weick, 1995, pp. 110-122).

It is true that existing mental models are continuously adapted and expanded on the basis of newly constructed meanings that are classified as plausible. The modified cognitive structures then guide future actions and are in turn continuously adapted by means of sensemaking. However, the core of the mental frame of reference remains unaffected by this further development (North, 1992, p. 87).

The process of sensemaking poses a major problem for the management of convergent innovation projects because the prevailing mental model is often applied to the development process without reflection. However, the perception and thought processes possible within these transferred cognitive structures are inadequate and do not meet the requirements, which then leads to a more restrictive intake and processing of information. The existing cognitive structures often select the incoming signals for the innovations to such an extent that important information that takes place at the edge of the market spectrum or is non-paradigmatic is not taken into account. Consequently, by behaving as an “information filter” a mental model can have a negative influence on innovation dynamics (Obloy & Obloy & Pratt, 2010, p. 168f.).

In addition, an innovation process must be regarded as a process of social construction of reality: the perception and information processing of each individual member of a company is integrated into the corporate culture. Based on the knowledge and experience that employees have gained in a similar form in the course of their work activities, a mutually shared mental model emerges at the collective level (see as a basis on the function of mutually shared mental models North, 1992, pp. 87-98).

With the help of these collectively shared thinking routines, the members of an organization filter the data that seems to make sense and integrate it into the existing innovation activity. The implemented innovation strategy in turn influences the company routines, which in turn act as information filters (Bettis & Prahalad, 1995; Obloy & Obloy & Pratt, 2010). Mutually shared mental models serve as a guide in the process of implementing knowledge in innovation processes (Bettis & Prahalad, 1995, p. 8). Thus, in innovation projects the assignment of meaning to new information also depends on what is considered correct within the company.

This then contradicts the idea, often postulated in research on convergent innovations, that new knowledge can be sought by means of strategic early detection (see e.g. Reichertz, 2015). More so, it is the organizational routines of action and procedure that determine whether the results of a strategic information search lead to action at all. Depending on the pattern of interpretation, companies will react differently to new knowledge or may completely miss it. Moreover, search routines only enable the discovery of knowledge that is already available.

In this context, it should be noted that new knowledge—which plays a central role in the process of industrial convergence—has yet to be created. Because convergent innovation processes are lacking adequate patterns of thinking, corresponding innovations can only be developed at high search costs. Companies therefore tend to be sluggish, i.e. their response is too slow and too weak. However, this also implies that inertia is a natural characteristic of convergent innovations, since new knowledge can only ever be learned against the background of existing knowledge.

Interestingly, research shows that richer mental models—measured by the number of cause and effect relationships contained within them—are not associated with higher performance. What is decisive is that the causal relationships stored within the mental model are consistent with the decision-making situation in innovation projects (see Gayry & Wood, 2011, p. 581).

It follows from the above that, in the context of innovation processes, it is not enough to acquire new

knowledge and modify existing thought structures. Rather, it is also necessary to abandon existing specific knowledge. The construction of a new mental model is only possible if existing thought patterns are “forgotten” and sufficient capacities for searching and processing information are made available. In this context, reference can be made to the cognitive creativity of the actors (Hesse, 1992). This ability allows individuals to think about situations that do not yet exist, in order to develop and try out new patterns of action. However, the content and significance of these innovations cannot be anticipated before they occur.

4. Promoting Absorptive Capacity

In the context of industrial convergence, companies find themselves in a decision-making situation with two relevant mental models (Obloy & Obloy & Pratt, 2010, p. 158): the company's internal knowledge base, on the one hand, and new external knowledge, on the other, which is to be transferred to the organizational knowledge base for the purpose of building up new competencies. However, a company can feasibly seek, incorporate, and utilize external knowledge within its internal knowledge base only to the extent it can be connected. The greater the gap between the existing knowledge base and the knowledge to be acquired, the lower the capacity to absorb external knowledge (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990; Ströh, 2014; Sutter, 2013).

The knowledge already existing in a company is decisive for whether external knowledge is identified as relevant at all and whether it can be merged with the organizational knowledge base. The incapability to appropriate new knowledge from the corporate environment is thus a cause of corporate rigidities. The concept of absorptive capacity (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990) offers an explanation as to why, for example, digital business models were generally developed by young companies.

The dynamics of technological progress make it crucial to acquire missing knowledge through cooperation. However, many companies are reluctant to cooperate due to a strong fear of an unwanted knowledge drain. Yet cooperation can be an important instrument of organizational learning. If one or more members of an organization tap into knowledge sources outside their own company, new knowledge can be acquired and integrated into their own company organization. For a cooperation to lead to the desired result, the organization must absorb the cooperation partner's knowledge as well as contribute its own experience knowledge to the cooperation. Only through mutual learning processes can new knowledge be created and integrated into the existing knowledge base (see Sutter, 2013, p. 135). Mental barriers to cooperation must be broken down.

A central aspect of acquiring new knowledge and initiating learning effects is the cooperation partners' so-called absorptive capacity. This includes the ability to absorb, acquire, and assimilate external knowledge (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990, p. 25). However, the integration of external knowledge is not an automated process. If, for example, the transfer involves knowledge about technological contexts, then the responsible persons of the two cooperation partners may combine completely different contents under the same term definitions. This can be attributed to the fact that many technical terms are unspecified as such and are only filled with content when transferred to a concrete context.

In the context of cooperation relationships, it is necessary to invest in learning processes. New knowledge can only be optimally absorbed without special conditions if the participating cooperation partners have similar knowledge bases. The absorption capacity depends on the already existing knowledge base, the ability to absorb new knowledge, and the joint generation of knowledge (Ströh,

2014, p. 15; Sutter, 2013, p. 130).

Since the assimilation of new knowledge is not an automatic process, the development of appropriate interaction activities and the ability to absorb and integrate knowledge plays a central role. The cooperation partners' absorptive capacity must thus be increased in a targeted and coordinated manner. An ongoing joint practice of knowledge transfer is an important prerequisite for the transfer of knowledge. By overlapping different practices, the cooperation partners can better transfer new knowledge and integrate it into their existing knowledge structures.

Cooperation partners can increase their absorptive capacity using a multi-stage approach (see Sutter, 2013, pp. 135-210). The first step is to create a common basis of communication between the cooperation partners. At the start of an innovation project, the participants must reach a mutual understanding of the innovation to be developed, so as to allow any goal-oriented work at all. For this purpose, they exchange knowledge in a broad and general manner (Sutter, 2013, p. 134). In contrast, detailed knowledge must be transferred between specialists should problems occur, for example, at the interface of subtasks. As this knowledge is very specific, it only needs to be exchanged between the specialists who work directly at the interface.

A certain base of common knowledge is indispensable for coordinated knowledge integration. A mutual understanding of the problem arises from the process of defining the characteristics of the innovation project to be developed and from making the first considerations on how the idea could be realized. In this context, one can also speak of knowledge bridging: for this purpose, an interactive question-answer process is developed. Step by step, a bridge is built between the expertise of both specialists until there is enough shared expertise to work in a coordinated manner (Sutter, 2013, p. 141).

In a second step, the integration and creation of new knowledge is achieved through modularization and prototyping (Sutter 2013, p. 148). Modularization describes the breaking down of an overall task into part components, and it enables specialists to work largely independently and autonomously on their subject-specific subtasks. This reduces to a minimum the necessary exchange of knowledge with specialists from other disciplines who are working on other subtasks. Prototyping refers to a trial-and-error process that enables the combination of individual knowledge modules. Ideas or work results are presented to other project members ("trial"). Then in a thought experiment, they assess whether the ideas are feasible or whether there might be integration problems ("Error") (Sutter 2013, p. 163).

In the process of prototyping, a specialist explains a certain issue from his perspective and tests this view against the knowledge of the other specialists. This process continues until no more errors can be identified. Through prototyping, individual knowledge is transferred into the knowledge base of the organization, for example, into a new product. A particular feature of mental prototyping, so called as it is initially only a mental process (Sutter, 2013, p. 148), is that it enables specialists to integrate their knowledge without having to share a lot of it because they can work relatively independently on their subtasks. At the same time, specialists do not have to expound on their knowledge in order to explain it to other specialists.

Once the mental prototyping process no longer detects any problems, the almost finished product is tested virtually, for example, through simulations. Rules, documents, and the developed prototypes and procedures themselves serve as media for integrating and storing the specialized knowledge (Sutter, 2013, p. 182). In this context, it is of great importance that the specialists define their knowledge on the basis of their considerations and their area of expertise. One also speaks of "boundary objects":

knowledge is documented from the specific perspective of a specialist. Examples of boundary objects include technical objects, plans, concepts, prototypes, and graphics.

Presenting the respective facts from their perspective in boundary objects allows other specialists to access the content, which in turn facilitates communication between the specialists. Boundary objects can also help to adapt existing behavioral patterns and thus promote learning. The presentation of knowledge from the respective specialist area (boundary objects) allows new perspectives to be taken into consideration (Sutter, 2013, p. 182).

5. Next Steps / Further Action

The first step was to conduct a literature research and review of cross-industry innovations. The next step is to produce an overview of the technologies used in the selected industrial sectors and create possible future scenarios based on them. These future scenarios are to be created depending on and in combination with adjacent industries and reviewed through expert interviews. Finally, it should be possible to make initial recommendations for the industries concerned.

References

- Bach, N. (2000). *Mentale Modelle als Basis von Implementierungsstrategien* [Mental models as the basis for implementation strategies] (Gabler Edition Wissenschaft). Wiesbaden: Deutscher Universitätsverlag.
- Bainbridge, W. S. (2006). Transformative concepts in scientific convergence. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1093, 24-45.
- Bierly, P. & Chakrabarti, A. K. (1999). Managing through industry fusion. In K. Brockhoff (Ed.), *The dynamics of innovation. Strategic and managerial implications* (pp. 5-26). Berlin: Springer.
- Bierly, P. & Chakrabarti, A. (1996). Generic knowledge strategies in the U.S. pharmaceutical industry. *Strategic Management Journal*, 17 (52), 123-135.
- BITKOM (Bundesverband Informationswirtschaft, Telekommunikation und neue Medien e.V.) (Ed.) (2005). *Digitale Konvergenz. Empfehlungen* [Digital convergence. Recommendations.]. Berlin. <https://www.bitkom.org/sites/default/files/file/import/Digitale-Konvergenz-final-v11.pdf>
- Brusoni, S. & Pavitt, K. (2003). *Problem solving and the co-ordination of innovative activities* (SPRU Electronic Working Paper Series Nr. 93), Brighton, Milano.
- Cohen, W.M. & Levinthal, D.A. (1990). Absorptive capacity: A new perspective on learning and innovation. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 35 (2), 128-152.
- Curran, C.-S., Bröring, S. & Leker, J. (2010). Anticipating converging industries using publicly available data. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 77 (3), 385-395.
- Dürmüller, C. & Enkel, E. (2013). Cross-Industry-Innovation: Der Blick über den Gartenzaun [Cross-Industry Innovation: Peeking over the garden fence]. In O. Gassmann & P. Sutter (Ed.), *Praxiswissen Innovationsmanagement. Von der Idee zum Markterfolg* [Practical knowledge innovation management. From the idea to market success] (3rd revised and expanded edition, pp. 195-214). München: Hanser Verlag.
- European Commission (Ed.). (1997). *Grünbuch zur Konvergenz der Branchen Telekommunikation, Medien und Informationstechnologie und ihren ordnungspolitischen Auswirkungen. Ein Schritt in Richtung Informationsgesellschaft* [Green Paper on the convergence of the telecommunications, media and information technology sectors and its regulatory implications. A step towards the information society] (Kom-(97) Nr. 623), Brüssel.
- Gary, M. & Wood, R.E. (2011). Mental models, decision rules, and performance heterogeneity. *Strategic Management Journal*, 32 (6), 569-594.
- Hamel, G. (1996). Strategy as revolution. *Harvard Business Review* (July-August). <https://hbr.org/1996/07/strategy-as-revolution> (01.08.2019)
- Hesse, G. (1992). Innovative Anpassung in sozio-ökonomischen Systemen. [Innovative adaptations in socio-economic systems] In B. Biervert & H. Held M (Ed.), *Evolutorische Ökonomik*. [Evolutionary economics] pp. 110-142. Frankfurt am Main: Campus.
- Hinden, D. (2007). Von Powerjoghurt und anderen Superkräften. Functional Food [On power yoghurt and other superpowers. Functional Food]. *Beobachter* [Observers]. <https://www.beobachter.ch/ernahrung/lebensmittel/functional-food-von-powerjoghurt-und-anderen-superkraefen>
- Kerl, A. (2018). *Management von Multi-Cross-Industry Innovation*. [Multi-cross-industry innovation management]. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien.
- Kogut, N. & Zander U. (1992). Knowledge of the Firm, Combinative Capabilities, and the Replication of Technology. *Organization Science*, 3 (3), 383-397.

- Lang, G. (2003). *Time Konvergenz. Einige Überlegungen aus volkswirtschaftlicher Sicht* [Time convergence. A few considerations from an economic perspective] (Volkswirtschaftliche Diskussionsreihe Nr. 234). Augsburg: Universität Augsburg.
- Lee, K.R. (2015). Toward a new paradigm of technological innovation: convergence innovation. *Asian Journal of Technology Innovation*, 23 (sup1), 1-8.
- Müller, K. (2008). *Strategieprozess und Marktkonvergenz. Der Zusammenhang zwischen unternehmensstrategischem Handeln, Unternehmensstrategie und konvergierenden Märkten aus der Perspektive der Strukturierungstheorie. Mit einem Beispiel aus dem Bereich Mobile TV* [Strategy process and market convergence. The connection between corporate strategic action, corporate strategy, and converging markets from the perspective of structuring theory. With an example from the field of mobile TV] (Dissertation). Universität Flensburg.
- Neisser, U. (1996). *Kognition und Wirklichkeit: Prinzipien und Implikationen der kognitiven Psychologie* [Cognition and Reality: Principles and implications of cognitive psychology]. Stuttgart: Klett-Cotta
- North, D.C. (1992). *Institutionen, institutioneller Wandel und Wirtschaftsleistung* [Institutions, institutional change, and economic performance]. Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck.
- Obloy, T. & Obloy, K. & Pratt, M.G. (2010). Dominant logic and entrepreneurial firms' performance in a transition economy. *Entrepreneurship theory and practice*, 34 (2), 151-170.
- Roco, M. C. & Bainbridge, W. S. (2013). The new world of discovery, invention, and innovation: convergence of knowledge, technology, and society. *Journal of Nanoparticle Research*, 15 (9), 1946-1963.
- Song, C. h. (2016). *Früherkennung von konvergierenden Technologien* [Early detection of convergent technologies]. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien.
- Stieglitz, N. (2004). *Strategie und Wettbewerb in konvergierenden Märkten* [Strategy and competition in converging markets] (Gabler Edition Wissenschaft). Wiesbaden: Deutscher Universitätsverlag.
- Ströh, D. (2014). *Absorptive capacity of SMEs: an empirical analysis of the early phases in the process of external information absorption of German SMEs in the mechanical engineering industry*. Hamburg: Kovač.
- Sutter, M. (2013). *Probleme und Potentiale der Wissensintegration in Beratungsprojekten* [Problems and potentials of knowledge integration in consulting projects]. Wiesbaden: Springer Gabler.
- Weick, K.E. (1995). *Der Prozess des Organisierens* [The process of organizing]. Frankfurt am Main: Suhrkamp
- Wieland, R. A. (2007). Konvergenz aus Kundensicht [Convergence from the customer's perspective]. In A. Picot & A. Freyberg (Ed.), *Infrastruktur und Services - Das Ende einer Verbindung? Die Zukunft der Telekommunikation* [Infrastructure and Services - The end of a connection? The future of telecommunication] (pp. 43-67). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag.